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NRL/USNO TWO WAY TIME TRANSFER MODEM DESIGN AND TEST RESULTS

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Abstract

The Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) has developed a two way time transfer modem for the United States Naval Observatory (USNO). This modem in conjunction with a Very Small Aperture Terminal (VSAT) and a communication satellite can achieve sub nanosecond time transfer performance. The purpose of this paper is to present an overview of the hardware and software design of the digital modem showing its unique features and results of satellite testing. Time transfer performance is achieved in the hardware by a combination of stability, matching and calibration. Hardware stability is achieved by using synchronous digital methods in both the transmitter and receiver sections. Analog components are kept to a minimum and are wide band where possible to promote delay stability. Identical narrow band filters are used in the transmitter and the receiver section to help match temperature dependent delays. Time transfer between sites is a master slave technique, a master site transferring time to a network of slave sites. The master transmits first, specifically addressing a slave site and the slave site responds. This allows the master to operate on a predetermined schedule based on satellite availability, and the target to respond based only on signals it receives. Once communications has been established,

data is exchanged in both directions through the satellite, thus eliminating the need for an additional communication path. A personal computer (PC) is used for operator interface, modem control, data collection and processing. With this method, both sites can be automated. Initial tests have been conducted to evaluate and verify modem performance and reduce the effects of other systematic errors. Modem tests at a common location were performed by direct connection and through two VSAT's. Tests used a common oscillator to the two modems to examine optimum comparison conditions. The test results will be presented.

Design Philosophy

Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the principle of the two way measurement. If the hardware sections are matched and corrections are made for the Sagnac effect on the propagation path, the clock difference can be found by taking half the difference in the measurements.

The system uses a Spread Spectrum Pseudo-Random Number (PRN), Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA), Binary Phase-Shift Keying (BPSK), modulation to transmit timing pulses and data between modems. The hardware was designed with as much digital hardware as practical for stability and compatibility with other modem designs or other CDMA

systems.

Hardware

Time transfer performance is achieved in the hardware by a combination of stability, matching and calibration. Hardware stability is achieved by using synchronous digital methods for most of the system in both the transmitter and receiver sections, along with wide band analog components to promote delay stability and matched narrow band filters in transmitter and receiver sections for canceling temperature dependent delays. See figure 2.

Analog Hardware

The analog components of the receiver are a relay for testing, a filter to prevent aliasing, an attenuator to control signal levels and two amplifiers for gain. The analog parts of the transmitter are a free-running oscillator at seventy MHz, a bi-phase modulator to add the code and data on the signal, an attenuator to control drive to the VSAT, an amplifier for gain, a filter to limit bandwidth and a relay for testing. Except for the filters, all of the analog signal parts are wide band to achieve delay stability. The narrow band filters are identical and located close together to help canceling temperature dependent delays.

Analog Digital Interfaces

The interfaces between the analog and digital sections are a D flipflop that drives the bi-phase transmitter modulator and an Analog to Digital Convertor (ADC) in the receiver. All the interface functions are clocked with the same twenty-five MHz.

Digital Hardware

The digital section can be divided into two areas, the real time digital hardware functions and programmable functions.

The real time Digital Signal Processing (DSP) hardware functions consist of a transmit section, a receive section and a timing section.

Digital Transmitter Section

The transmitter section consists of a transmit code rate Numerically Controlled Oscillator (NCO) and code generator. The equation below is the standard equation for the output frequency of a 32 bit NCO.

$$\text{Output} = \text{Clock} * \text{Control} / 2^{32}$$

With a 32 bit NCO and a clock of twenty-five MHz the frequency steps are ~0.0058 Hz. The wanted frequency might be off by as much as half this step. To overcome this problem the control word to the NCO is switched for four clocks on each output cycle of the NCO to a value that is X higher than the control word. This reduces the effective size of the accumulator by 4X to

$$2^{32} - 4X.$$

The equation for the output frequency becomes

$$\text{Output} = \text{Clock} * \text{Control} / (2^{32} - 4X)$$

This allows both the numerator and denominator to be programmed giving almost an unlimited selection of output frequencies. In this system the transmit code rate NCO can be set at any frequency in steps of 1/n where n is any integer up to 42. One Hz steps are used to generate the one Pulse Per Second (PPS) synchronization pulse in the transmitter system. See figure 3.

Digital Receiver Section

The receiver contains a receive code rate NCO, code generator, carrier to baseband down conversion and correlators. The baseband down conversion uses a NCO to generate an In (I) phase and a Quadrature (Q) phase Local Oscillator (LO) signal to drive a pair of digital mixers (multipliers) forming the I and Q baseband signals. The I and Q baseband signals are both despread by an early and a late reference code in four accumulators or correlators. The four correlators output are an Early In phase (EI), a Late In phase (LI), an Early Quadrature phase (EQ), and a Late Quadrature phase (LQ). The correlator outputs go to the programmable DSP processor. See figure 4.

Timing Section

The timing section is synchronized to the external one PPS and five MHz and is used to control the transmitter and to time tag the received data. Part of the modem start-up is to synchronize the internal timing section to the external one PPS. The first step in synchronizing is to measure the peak amplitude of the external one PPS and set an input threshold based on the peak level. The level is measured by using a comparator with one input connected to the one PPS and the other input connected to a digital to analog convertor (DAC). The output of the DAC is increased until the output of the comparator is stable and then the comparator is set to a fraction of this level. The internal clock is twenty-five MHz and is derived by multiplying the five MHz input by five. The five MHz signal passes through an eight bit digitally controlled variable delay with a total range of about 50 nanoseconds and a resolution of approximately 0.2 nanosecond. The twenty-five MHz is connected to the D input of a D

flipflop with the one PPS connected clock of the flipflop. The D flipflop samples the phase of the twenty-five MHz on the second. The output of the flipflop can be monitored by the DSP processor. By varying the five MHz delay and monitoring the phase of the twenty-five MHz at the D flipflop, the internal twenty-five MHz clock can be synchronized to the one PPS independently of the phase of the five MHz, the phase shift in the multiplier and the amplitude of the one PPS. If the phase of the five MHz is known to be stable with respect to the one PPS, this system can be used to monitor the phase stability of the twenty-five MHz multiplier. This method has demonstrated a repeatability of .2 nanoseconds. See figure 6.

Most of the real time digital hardware can be configured by the software. Codes, code rates, code lengths, code types and sample rate are all programmable.

Hardware Test Points

The modem contains two digital test points and two analog test points. The test points were designed for product development and trouble shooting. The digital test points selection is controlled from the keyboard. Epochs, codes, code clocks for both transmitter and receiver, the receiver carrier nco frequency, and the one PPS input and output are some of the signals that are available at the digital test ports. There also are two analog test points. The analog test points are driven by a dual twelve-bit Digital to Analog Convertor (DAC). This DAC is driven in real time from the TMS320C30. Output rates can be in excess of fifty thousand samples per second. With the pair of DAC's it is possible to monitor the digital outputs of the correlators on an oscilloscope in real time.

Dual Processor Configuration

The system uses a dual processor configuration that communicate through a dual port memory. One processor is a Texas Instrument TMS320C30 DSP integrated circuit capable of 33 Million Floating Point Operations Per Second (MFLOPS) on 32 bit words. It is located in the backplane of the host processor an International Business Machine (IBM) compatible Personal Computer (PC), the other processor. The PC must have sixteen bit or larger backplane. The PC is used for operator interface, for data storage and to control the DSP processor. Both processors were programmed in C.

Codes

The modem uses a code generator chip with three independent code generators. The generators each use a 32 stages shift register with programmable taps to generate PRN codes. Also included in each code generators is a programmable initiation register that defines a start code and a programmable epoch register that generates a pulse when the generator reaches this pattern. Three programmable counters are also available. Any epoch or counter can be programmed to initialize any generator or counter. With this chip it is possible to generate maximum length sequences, non-maximum as Gold codes used by the Global Positioning System (GPS) System or other Ranging systems or truncated codes as used by the Hartl/Mitrex modem. The codes used in the modem are maximum length type with a length of 4095, and are selected to have low a cross correlation characteristic which has a peak value of 127. The feedback tap positions for these codes are 100000101001, 101000011000 and 110010100000 and the decimal equivalents 2089, 2584 and 3232. Figures 6 and 7 show some of the cross correlation characteristics of

the codes. The cross correlation of the above codes can induce errors in the tracking loops equal to the code chip period times one half the ratio between the cross correlation and the auto correlation functions. With a chip frequency of 2,489,760 Hz, this error could be as large as 6.2 nanoseconds. This error is based on only one code period and with equal carrier frequencies. Simulations on these codes show that carrier offsets can increase the cross correlation by about 3 db or up to about 8.8 nanoseconds. The cross correlation in the system is not just the cross correlation of the codes for one code period but is also changed by the difference in the carrier of the signals, the data modulation on the code and is an averaged over about five minutes of data. For the system where the code repeats at 608 Hz rate, the cross correlation of 182,400 code periods over 300 seconds should have a net effect significantly below the one nanosecond range.

Sampling Rate and Code Chip Rate

There are several factors driving the System Configuration. The bandwidth of the satellite channel limited the chip rate to approximately 2.5 MHz. A 600-bit-per-second data rate is needed to transfer data and general communication. Words of 32 bits help match the computer architecture. The 2.5 MHz bandwidth and the 600-bit-per-second rate lead to a code length of 4095 and 600 bits per second lead to 19 words of 32 bits per word. The product of 19, 32 and 4095 give a chip rate of 2,489,760 Hz. The selection of the ratio sampling rate and code chip rates is critical. The system code rate is 2,489,760 Hz and the sampling rate is twenty-five MHz. The highest common frequency is 160 Hz which corresponds to 156,250 clock cycles and 15561 code cycles. The sampling rate of

25,000,000 samples per second can lead to a problem with the Hartl/Mitrex modem. This Hartl/Mitrex modem code rate is 2,500,000 which is also the highest common frequency with the sampling rate. This commensurability problem would be a quantization of TOA measurements at 40 nanoseconds. Additional hardware is available in the modem to add phase noise to the output of the receive code rate NCO to correct this problem. This noise will have a uniform distribution over and a peak-to-peak range of forty nanoseconds. This addition takes place before the time quantization of forty nanoseconds.

Signal Search

A model of the four components of the correlator outputs is given below.

CORRELATOR OUTPUTS and LOOP FILTER INPUTS

M = SIGNAL MAGNITUDE
 R = CARRIER PHASE ERROR RADIANS
 C = CODE OFFSET ERROR IN CHIPS
 D = DATA MODULATION IN RADIANS

EI = IN PHASE EARLY
 EQ = QUADRATURE PHASE EARLY
 LI = IN PHASE LATE
 LQ = QUADRATURE PHASE LATE

For $-.5 < C < .5$
 $EI = M (.5 - C) \cos (R + D)$
 $EQ = M (.5 - C) \sin (R + D)$
 $LI = M (.5 + C) \cos (R + D)$
 $LQ = M (.5 + C) \sin (R + D)$

SIGNAL LEVEL SQUARED
 $M^2 = (EI + LI)^2 + (EQ + LQ)^2$

CODE LOOP INPUTS
 $C = (LI^2 - EI^2 + LQ^2 - EQ^2) / (2M^2)$

CARRIER LOOP INPUTS
 $R = \text{ARCTAN}((EQ+LQ)/(EI+LI))$

To acquire the signal, the correct

carrier frequency and phase and code phase must be found. The carrier frequency can be offset from nominal by the seventy MHz crystal at the transmitter, the VSAT oscillators, the satellite oscillator or the clock at receiver. The largest of these is the satellite and next the VSAT. The modem can be tuned over several MHz but the software search for the carrier is restricted to plus or minus 19 KHz from nominal. The code phase is unrestricted and a full code period search of 1.6 milliseconds is performed. To decrease acquisition time, a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is used to search for the unknown frequency while the reference code is slid to find the received code phase. The samples of the FFT are calculated by adding the early and late components of I and Q to form the complex samples. Normally during tracking the accumulators are sampled at the end of each code period for 608 samples per second rate, but during acquisition the sampling rate is increased 64 times to 38,912 samples per second. Blocks of 64 complex samples are saved, the length of one code period. The first sample of the block is synchronized with the code period to prevent possible cancellation if a data bit transition occurred in the middle of the block. An FFT is calculated on the block of 64 complex points. The output of the FFT is scanned to find the maximum frequency. If the energy at this frequency is significantly greater than average energy in all of the non-adjacent frequencies, a signal is assumed to be present. The search is performed over the entire code period to insure that the maximum peak signal is found and that the modem does not lock on to a lesser peak. After the peak is found an estimate on the frequency is calculated by looking at the magnitude of the largest frequency found by the FFT and the magnitude of the largest adjacent frequency. The carrier NCO is tuned by this calculation to

reduce this frequency from the output of the correlators to much less than 304 Hz. A second carrier NCO adjustment is made by watching for over a second the complex spinning rate on the output of the correlators. At this point the code phase and carrier frequency are close and the phase locked loops for both the carrier and code can be enabled.

Code and Carrier Tracking Loops

The error signal for the carrier loop is R and the code loop is C in the equations for the correlator outputs. A double argument arctangent routine could be used to solve for angle of the carrier and data phase errors, R+D, but the single argument arctangent routine produces an output that is independent of D. The PI ambiguity in the routine is the same as the data modulation. The DSP software calculates the value of C and R for carrier and code and they are used as inputs to two digital filters. The output of the filter is added to the approximate center frequency value and feeds the results are feed to the NCO. This forms the carrier or code phased locked loop. If C and D are within bounds, both loops are independent of M and D and the carrier loop is independent of C and the code loop is independent of R. This operation is done at the 608 Hz rate of the code epochs. Bit Synchronization The purpose of the bit synchronization is to mark the second point in the message. The synchronization word is 32-bits long for convenience. It is sixteen zeros followed by sixteen ones. This pattern was chosen to resolve the 180-degree phase ambiguity problem with bi-phase modulation, to use most of the ASCII character and to match the word size in the processor. Synchronization is recognized by looking for sixteen zeros followed by sixteen ones or by looking for sixteen ones followed by sixteen

zeros. The significance of the latter is that the carrier loop tracks 180-degrees out of phase. If this happens data is decoded by simply inverting each bit.

Time Of Arrival Calculations

The Time Of Arrival (TOA) is not measured directly. The code loops generates a reference code that tracks the incoming signal. The timing of the reference loop is measured at a 608 Hz rate. This measurement is made at each code epoch. The epoch time is measured to 40 nanoseconds by counting the twenty-five MHz clock. The phase of the reference code clock is measured by reading the accumulator of the reference code clock NCO. With a code clock of 2,489,760 Hz and a twelve-bit phase measurement the time of the epoch can be measured to less than one hundred picoseconds. By looking for the synchronization pulse the one second epoch can be recognized. The measurements are reduced by using a least squares linear fit calculated on the 608 measurements centered around the one second epoch. The variance is also calculated. The TMS320C30 is only a single precision (32 bit) floating point processor. The mantissa of a 32-bit floating point word has 24 bits of precision which is not enough precision for our results. By removing the known slop characteristics of the data before the linear fit the results can be calculated and interpolated by the TMS320C30.

Operation

Time transfer between sites is a master slave technique, a master site transferring time to a network of slave sites. The master transmits first, specifically addressing a slave site and the slave site responds. This allows the master to operate on a predetermined schedule

based on satellite availability, and the target to respond based only on signals it receives. Once communications has been established, data is exchanged in both directions through the satellite, thus eliminating the need for an additional communication path. The PC is used for operator interface, modem control, data collection and processing. With this method, both sites can be automated.

Data

Data is transmitted between the two modems. This data contains a synchronization pulse that repeats every second, time of day, measurement, and station identification information. There is also area in the format for general purpose communication. The source of the general purpose communication data is taken from a disc file on the PC and is passed through the dual port ram to the DSP system. The DSP merges this data with the synchronization pulse, time of day and measurements. Using the Direct Memory Access (DMA) interrupt and serial port features of the TMS320C30, a serial bit stream drives an exclusive or circuit in the transmit code generator. The received data is processed by the DSP system. Working with the data from the correlators it searches for the synchronizing pulse and resolves the 180 degree ambiguity of the data. This information is then passed through the dual port memory to the PC where it is split and the parts are stored in different files.

Test Results

Initial tests have been conducted to evaluate and verify modem performance and reduce the effects of other systematic errors. Modem tests at a common location were performed with single and dual VSAT's. All tests used a common oscillator and

location to the two modems to examine modem stability. A pair of power dividers were used at seventy MHz and the single VSAT case to connect the two modems to the VSAT. No attempt was made to match cable lengths or calibrate the modems. The test did not examine the effects of cross correlation because of the common clock and common up-link distance. Future tests to examine cross correlation will use an offset between the oscillators of the two modems to look at the non-linear characteristics in time transfer data. Two distance locations will also show cross correlation problems but additional information will be needed to separate clock and range changes from the cross correlation problems. For most of the test a 200 pico seconds noise level was showed on the data with day-to-day repeatability below this level. Two problems have been seen in the data. The data on a pass-to-pass basis will occasionally jump twenty nanoseconds due to a twenty-five MHz clock slip in one unit, half a clock period. Faster chips are going to be used to fix this problem. A second problem is a discrete change of one to two nanoseconds. This problem has not been pinpointed at the present time. Figures 8 and 9 show the performance of the modem and figures 10 and 11 show the two modem problems.

Figure 5

Reference Input Circuit and Internal Clock Synchronization

Figure 6

Cross Correlation, Code Taps: 2089, 3232

Figure 7

Cross Correlation, Code Taps: 2089, 2584

